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Insecurity and the Challenges of Developmental States in Africa: The Case of Nigeria

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Abstract

Security is predominantly a critical factor in achieving a developmental state, and also an ideal condition characterised as sustained development. In Africa, such has been witnessed, experience has shown that insecurity undermines the proactive actions and activities of key elements and factors linked to national development, such as political, economic, and socio-cultural interactions amongst others, which are all synchronized towards attaining and creating a situation of safety, reduction of poverty and inequalities, peaceful interaction and rapid, almost-even growth. The Nigerian state is besieged by numerous problems, both internally and externally, which are contributing to slowing down its national development objective, and the needs, aspirations and expectations of the citizenry. The concerns surrounding insecurity, especially human security as pertaining to all six geographical regions covering the North, South, East and West, have not been fully addressed. Hence, no reprieve nor lasting solutions, but rather a rapid increase in insecurity causing death, suffering, and displacements of Nigerian citizens, further worsening the troubles of attaining development, developmental state status and growth in Nigeria. The methodology adopted was the qualitative descriptive approach, which helped to identify and analyse materials used for the content development of the article. Social conflict and human security theoretical frameworks were used to explain the realities and nexus between development (al) states, and security. Findings show that there is a link between security and development, especially as development and growth have been correlated with the availability of security that encompasses lives, property, and well-being.

Keywords: Security, Sustainable, Developmental State, Nigeria

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Insecurity and the Challenges of Developmental States in Africa: The Case of Nigeria**Introduction**

Within the 21st century, countries in Africa, Asia, Europe, and Latin America are still confronted with the same old problem of economic development, governance and political stability, insecurity, declining and stagnant manufacturing sector, unemployment and poverty. Development and sustainable growth of any form is still elusive for a large number of these nations, particularly in Africa, where a vast majority of nations still suffer from the underdevelopment/developing syndrome, not because they do not have resources in abundance, educated and skilled manpower, nor the initiative and reason to attain this stage. Rather, the driving force has been a negative trend of conflict and crisis, supported by pedestrian political leadership and public administrators, economic sabotage and unaccountability, religious and ethnic bias, a large dose of insecurity, amongst many more.

The developmental state not only refers to the collective economic and human development, but also describes the state's essential role in harnessing national resources and directing incentives through a distinctive policy-making process" (Ng, 2008). It is a collective endeavour, focused on the state and private apparatus within states, to engender both development and security in a state. Meanwhile, the inference towards the nexus between developmental state and security has been given increased attention by policymakers, governments, and organisations at various levels. Such as by former UN General secretary Kofi Annan that, "humanity will not enjoy development without security and will not enjoy security without development and will not enjoy either without respect for human rights" (Johanssen, 2014: 1). Therefore, as one can see in the

quotation above, security and developments are linked together in a mutually reinforcing relationship and when one of these factors is not met the mutuality are weakened and as a result neither security or development can be attained" (Johanssen, 2014: 2).

In Africa, the potential of 'developmental states' has been an ongoing debate referred to as the impossibility theorem, which is expressed in the 'impossibility-of-a-developmental-state-in-Africa theory, and is majorly because the, "internal conditions of many African states: unending civil wars, pervasive corruption, dependence syndrome, lack of autonomy, rent-seeking behavior, neo-patrimonialism, lack of democratic institutions, unaccountable governments, and lack of adequate educational opportunities for the continent's teeming youth population, among others" (Nwapi & Andrew, 2017: p 236). Also "the scholarship concerning the developmental state and Africa, centers around the question of whether or not the model is possible outside of Asia, and the possibility that only four countries of Botswana, Mauritius, South Africa, and Uganda discussed largely in literature as likely developmental states present in Africa" (Nwapi & Andrew, 2017; Ghebremusse, 2015; Mailafia, 2020). Recently Rwanda and Ethiopia have been included into the developmental state group, "due to their stellar growth, expanding possible frontiers of welfare and improved livelihood for millions of their citizens" (Mailafia, 2020), as against other countries regarded as giants in Africa.

This recurrent development/developmental state debate is very much audible and unending within the Nigerian political-economic and social scene, centred around the true status of development amongst the six

geo-political zones and the whole country. This is mostly due to the glaring nonexistence and unevenness of internal development around the country, and so rather than the begging question of how the essence of a developmental state if achieved can be of immense benefit and increase to every Nigerian within and in every part of the world, instead there exist politicization of spending, projects and issues such as the quota system (education, employment and economy), and a rising situation of insecurity from state and non-state actors that has taken center stage over concurrent issues of national concern. The article is structured into 6 parts. It includes the abstract, introduction, methodology, body of the article, conclusion and recommendations, and references.

Method

This is a quantitative research study, utilising the descriptive approach in the article writing to investigate the dynamic linkup and connection between security and the case for developmental states in Africa, particularly Nigeria. Primary sources of data examined and used to generate information were obtained from documents, books, academic articles, and Newspapers relevant to the topic's purpose and aim on security, developmental state, and the possibility of a security-developmental state nexus.

The Development Paradigm

Development in whatever ramification is conceptually and practically delicate to handle. More often than not, development refers to initiatives and mechanisms that are often pro-poor and broad-based in nature; sets of practices that guide and structure social change processes geared towards improving the living conditions of people in a particular geopolitical locale (Nwapi & Andrew, 2017). It is a concept that reflects its impact through the people as the main beneficiaries of such efforts to enhance their standard of living and

wellbeing. It is humanistic and hence described as,

Been couched in terms of material things, rather than people, in terms of creation, rather than evolution, true development must mean the development of man; it is also clear that development does not start with goods and things; it starts with people (Isong, 1985: 3)

Simply put, development is defined as enhanced well-being and human flourishing, particularly as the fundamental nature of development. Furthermore, a developmental state is the absence of irrelevance, particularly in leadership, bias in its developmental blueprint and policy implementation, and focused on 'how states can become more capable and more supportive of development and human security' (Fritz & Menocal, 2007: p 531). These are some of the primary considerations of development initiatives and interventions, which will instigate the push for a developmental state, especially in Africa and Nigeria.

The Developmental State and Africa

The developmental state has "been a global paradigm for how states can play a positive role in social and economic development" (Evans & Heller, 2018), a positive impact transformation of society and the lives of the people. It is viewed in terms of economic development, prosperity, political maturity in leadership and decision making, and an affirmative social change. Developmental states are not isolated in themselves in reference to development goals, but refer to initiatives and mechanisms that are often pro-poor and broad-based in nature. In essence, development underscores the discourses and sets of practices that guide and structure social change processes geared" (Nwapi & Andrews, 2017: 229) towards a state attaining the status of a developmental state.

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The possibilities of ‘developmental states’ in Africa have become a subject of interest for scholars, development practitioners and African leaders (Routley, 2014, p. 159). This is especially with the “success of developmental states achieved in East Asia by countries like Singapore, Taiwan and Hong Kong, as well as the efforts of many African states to regain control over the exploitation of their resources and take charge of their development have generated significant scholarly interest globally” (Nwapi & Andrews, 2017: 227). At its core, “the developmental state is committed to economic development, and is generally characterized as a state that intervenes and guides the direction of economic growth” (Ghebremusse, 2015: 2).

According to Routley, “the developmental state as a ‘buzzword’ encompassing a range of attributes, such as prosperity, wellbeing, efficiency and growth” (2014: 172), it is the idea of state-led development that is closely related to the concept of “industrial policy” state-intervention in economic activity (Nwapi & Andrews, 2017: 230). Consequently, the pursuit of a developmental state can thus imply the pursuit of a novel mode for achieving development, and this can contribute towards a future-oriented rhetoric which, in turn, can be productive of the commitment identified as necessary within the developmental-state literature.

Developmental states have defining features and characteristics, and these manifestations are largely lacking in the majority of African states. According to Mkandawire in Ghebremusse (2015: 6 & 7), these are divided into two broad categories: ideological and structural. He contends that this ideology-structure nexus distinguishes developmental states from other states; ideologically, the developmental state is “developmentalist” and its mission is that of ensuring economic

development, usually interpreted to mean high rates of accumulation and industrialisation. Structurally, ‘the developmental state isn’t defined by its capacity to implement economic policies sagaciously and effectively, which is determined by such factors as institutions, technology, politics, and administration. Therefore, African states must consider, readjust and align state policy as well as effort, and importantly, fully involve the citizens because ‘it is the citizens that will generate that development, through active participation as it is a vital development ingredient of the developmental state’ (Nwapi & Andrews, 2017: 225). As an alternative, “additional measures and checks, such as poverty levels and human capacity, can also be used to conclude whether the state meets the structural criteria, through improvements to such areas of the day-to-day lives of the broader population can help entrench the state in society and enhance its legitimacy, thus supporting a sustainable developmental state and ensuring its success” (Ghebremusse, 2015: 7).

In order to achieve the developmental state project in Africa, it is not enough to have a developmental ideology and structures; it is equally essential that the African states demonstrate in unmistakable terms that they are serious about pursuing development, attaining and maintaining that status, with all available state resources, amid accountability and synergy. This is rightly so, because accountable leadership in synergy with every facet of its society guarantees a policy of redistribution that reaches every geopolitical region of the country (Routley: 2014, Evans & Heller, 2018, Nwapi & Andrews, 2017), which will result in sustained positivity and growth. Present day African leaders, of which few can be counted as having been very proactive to influence the direction of their state activities (politically, economically and

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socio-culturally) to evolve sustainability, have been criticized for been excessively self-serving and power hungry, and ‘scholars argue that consolidating power was another objective that detracted African leaders from developmentalism’ (Ghebremusse, 2015: 10). Ake (1996) emphasized this argument by stating that state interventions and resources were not entirely used to promote development, but rather “to facilitate the appropriation of wealth using state power”. Hence, the element of a focused, responsive and forward-thinking leadership is an invaluable asset that African leaders must adapt to meet the ambitions of the state and its citizens. However, there is upward optimism for a better economic future for Africa that can be observed; it is stimulated by the success of East Asian states, most of which found themselves in conditions much worse than those faced by most African states today’ (Nwapi & Andrews, 2017: 237)

Nigeria: Developmental State and Security

Since the dawn of mankind, the quest for security has been the’ predominant reason for the formation of communities and ultimately states (Winkler, 2003: 14). It is a global concern of our contemporary time, without exception, and encompasses both internal and the external realities of threats to its achievement and sustenance of the state and its citizens, a fact that is evident during any form of national or international crisis that threatens the survival of states (Josephs, 2016: 6). Such instances include the Corona virus (COVID 19) pandemic that ravaged the world in 2020, has shown that only states with forward thinking responsive leadership and government will get through with less loss of life, a more than adequate health care system and a citizenry that has adjusted to the system due to the existence of opportunities for citizen participation in the state and development process.

National security is a concept that covers absolutely all aspects of human life, the state and its roles (national, international), interests and developmental aims (Josephs, 2016: 42 & 43). It is a major foundational part for initiating development and attaining the expanding reality of a developmental state and is predominantly assured in “a state or condition where our most cherished values and beliefs, our democratic way of life, our institutions of governance and our unity, welfare and well-being as a nation and people are permanently protected and continuously enhanced” (De La Salle University, 2013: 1). The most essential function of any government is to provide peace and security for its people, as there can be no development without peace, meaning that “contemporary security and development related challenges rarely occur in isolation and they are inextricably linked” (Dursun-Ozkanca, 2021: 1). Nigeria’s developmental state objectives have suffered tremendous setbacks, particularly in all vital aspects of state development achieved through cohesive effort and integration. Economic, political and socio-cultural efforts have been tainted with miserable pedestrian or worse copycat policies that do not reflect, affect or change the true situation within Nigeria. This abject situation has created the dire consequences of poverty and insecurity, which have been manipulated and exploited through the actions and activities of state and non-state actors for political reasons and economic gains.

Nigeria’s economic recovery was dampened by the report of the Economic Advisory Council (EAC) led by Doyin Salami. The report stated that the economy has been growing sluggishly at a painfully slow pace of 1.9% in gross domestic product, while the population has been expanding faster than the economy at an average of 2.6% (*Punch Newspaper*, 2020: p 24). In 2018, due to loss

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of revenue, dwindling FDI's, mismanagement of resources and corruption, Nigeria started been referred to somewhat as the poverty capital of the world (*Punch Newspaper*, 2020: p 24), depicting an ever-deepening agenda of poverty and misery for the citizens, as well as a widening occurrence of rich versus poor, increasing situations of unrest, dissatisfaction with the political class, leadership and eventually society.

Nigeria has been clouded with problems of insecurity rising from politics, ethnic/tribal crises, religious violence, economic crisis, and, in recent times, by extremist religious fundamentalists. The rate and growth of pockets of dissatisfaction has exploded to encompass individuals and groups armed and unarmed, seeking economic and political gains under the cover of religious drive, Boko Haram, kidnapping, banditry, armed robbery, killings, assassination and an uncontrolled proliferation of small arms and light weapons. The security forces, Police and Military that are meant to protect the lives and freedom of the Nigerian people have themselves become agents of death and terror, killing innocent and guilty discreetly and in the open with aplomb. Individual, group and national security are at an all-time low and 10 points away from hitting rock bottom and imploding. Without doubt, the importance of development to national security cannot be ignored nor overemphasised due to its major contribution to peace and stability internally. Without security, there can simply be no sustained development, nor any progress in democratic tenets, stability and peace (Winkler, 2003: 16).

Theoretical Framework

This article adopts two theoretical frameworks: social conflict theory to analyse the social interactions within the society, and human security theory, which highlights the necessity of security in engendering

development and growth in states through actions and policies targeted at particular problems and issues of predominance.

Medler et.al (2008) identified Social Conflict theory as “used to explain the interactions between societies during times of turmoil and change”. Galtung (2009) describes the theory “as a special case of incompatibility, a situation where actors use conflict behaviour against each other to attain incompatible goals and or to express their hostility”. Conflict revolves around a competition for scarce resources among actors and structures in society. It could also be as a result of dislocation in society, such as ethnic, racial, gender and religious” (Ritzer, 2008: 62). Social Conflict theory is based on two fundamental factors: conflict as a result of structural infirmities in society, and conflict as a result of the actions and activities of actors within society and outside of society.

On structural conflict, Faleti (2006: 41) writes that this form of conflict is built into the particular ways societies are structured and organised. The theory looks at social problems like political and economic exclusion, injustice, poverty, disease, exploitation and inequity as sources of conflict. A realistic example is the Marxist theory of economic inequality based on the unequal exploitative relationship between the capitalist bourgeoisie and proletariat in production and societal relations as the major source of conflict. Also, in social relations and interactions, there is often a struggle for scarce resources amongst individuals and group actors, which results in conflict and crises. Hence, the actor influenced the form of conflict. A social relation defines the broad set of expectations which outline the rights and obligations of individuals within society. The ability of the system to meet these expectations fully determines most time peace and conflict in a society.

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The human security approach, a redefinition of conventional security, was initiated in 1994. It aims to “transform traditional notions of security, framed in terms of national and regional stability and the stability of political and economic systems, and to focus on human beings. Hence, the guarantee of national security no longer lay in military power, but in favorable social, political, and economic conditions, the promotion of human development, and the protection of human rights” (Tadjbakhsh, 2005: 5). According to Samadi and Mirabbassi (2016), the ‘human security’ approach argues that threats and challenges to security transcend national defence, and law and order to encompass all political, economic and social issues that guarantee a life free from risk and fear. Its focus has shifted from the State to the security of persons; however, these are not mutually exclusive as security of the citizens is protection of state interest and vice versa”. Human security approach also clarified that any “attempt to address security related matters needs to be based on consultation and collaboration with different sets of actors which frequently have different interests, such as civilian/military; governmental/non-governmental; and local/national/regional/international organizations or agencies” (Samadi & Mirabbassi, 2016).

Proponents of human security theory believe that when the basic needs of an individual, especially pertaining to his/her continued existence, livelihood, and self-worth/respect, are met, the individual will experience a significant rise in the quality of their standard of living and as such will be less likely to recourse to violence over values and interests. As Olufu-Adeoye (2013) contends, “if these needs are not met, the individual or group feels humiliated, unrecognized and not taken seriously, acquiescing to violent

manifestations. She further states that “sustainable development demands that all people must have access to the basic conditions of life, which include health, water, biodiversity, agriculture and energy”. Therefore, social conflicts and widespread ‘human’ insecurity are prominent in states that lack developmental state initiative and structures. Also, in situations where the state structures are unable to provide basic services and security, the concept of ‘failed/fragile state’ often applies, as in the case of Nigeria, where poverty, the general well-being, and standard of living are in dire condition. Underscoring factors that suggest the ideals of developmental states, and security in whatever ramifications are presently unachievable, and may never be within current political, economic, and social conditions prevalent in Nigeria.

Implications of Insecurity on Nigeria’s Developmental Objective

Political Impact of insecurity on Nigeria’s developmental objectives: If a developmental state is described according to Meyns and Musamba as “one whose ideological underpinnings are developmental and ‘focused’ on serious attempts to deploy its administrative and political resources to the task of economic development” (2010: 10). Hence, developmental goals are linked and conceived from peaceful and forward-thinking states, and according to Odi (2007, cited in Nwokorie, 2014) developmental states have clearly defined vision, leadership and a sense of national purpose. Therefore, political stability, focused proactive leadership, which is enhanced by efficient public services, are all integral aspects of any developmental drive or initiative in any society. Political instability is a negative trend and a vital recipe for underdevelopment and further crises. Nigeria has, over time, been bedevilled with political crises in a persistent

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and multifaceted sphere, both at the federal, state and local level, especially between and within the two dominant political parties of the Peoples Democratic Party (PDP), and the ruling All Progressive Congress (APC), their members and party supporters. The constant bickering has detracted from the task of nation-building and creating cohesion through unity of purpose for the development of Nigeria. Instead, ethnic, tribal and religious sentiments are harped upon, furthering the divide, slow and uneven underdevelopment of Nigeria. It has seriously destabilised, stalled and led to confusion about the Nigerian development objective, a challenge that is yet to be addressed with a viable solution. Political instability vis-à-vis insecurity is most times caused by one or the other. It is imperative that it is a weakness that could lead to the inevitable destruction of any country, particularly Nigeria. Insecurity that allows the damaging and divisive activities results in political instability, or political instability that results in insecurity allows for state and non-state actors to derail developmental state objectives. Such groups include political parties and their members who field unqualified and corrupt candidates, regional inclined and favored socio-cultural/political groups, and fundamentalist religious groups like Boko Haram who seek to install a caliphate, Ansaru and some others who kidnap, kill and caused forced internal migration; as also national and multinational groups who seek economic gains and resources by either destabilizing or controlling the state through proxies.

Economic Impact of insecurity on Nigeria's developmental objectives: Developmental states have become “a generic term to describe governments that try to actively ‘intervene’ in economic processes and direct the course of development rather than relying only on market forces” (Stubbs, 2009, p. 5) of demand

and supply. It is unfortunate that the economic policies and agendas of various Nigerian governments, following full democratic status since 1999, have fallen short of the requirement to activate and bolster economic prosperity and infrastructural development within the country. Insecurity has further worsened any economic objective of the government, as state and non-state actors have continued to act to the detriment of national economic and developmental policies. These crises have also undermined regulation in the Nigerian infrastructure sector, as many of these crises, especially in the northern part of the country, have affected viable structures, economic buildings, roads, health facilities and airports.

Insecurity that results in conflicts and crises is/are familiar occurrence in non-developmental, underdeveloped and disorganised states with economic vulnerability and calamity. This features a lack of sustenance and implementation of economic policies, particularly during a change in government, which Nigeria is very culpable for, where further opportunities are stifled and disrupted by the mostly unhindered activities of bandits, kidnappers, religious bigots and fundamentalists, ethnic bigots and miscreants, which will surely cripple the country economically sooner rather than later. There is also an inadequate or non-existent maintenance of the existing stock of infrastructural facilities. Moreover, in Nigeria, maintenance is less preferred to new construction projects, which offer more opportunities for corruption in terms of kickbacks and outright embezzlement. All of these with negative implications on the efficiency of the role, costs, and even security of human resources, who are important agents for economic growth and infrastructural development.

Human and Socio-Cultural Impact of Insecurity on Nigeria's Developmental objectives:

Human and socio-cultural interactions are important aspects of any developmental state initiative. Humans as agents of development are involved in every phase of decision making, policy initiation/implementation and production of goods and services to enhance the economy. Therefore, insecurity hinders the efficient and effective utilisation of human resources in ensuring, as well as fast-tracking, the delivery of sustainable development in a developmental state setting. Insecurity breeds fear, instability and stagnant underdevelopment; for instance, during the early surge of Boko Haram in Northern Nigeria, the Human Rights Watch (HRW) (cited in Josephs, 2016) report reveals that in 2011 alone, "Boko Haram struck 115 times and killed 550 people". This figure of casualties has increased to hundreds of thousands over the years, and properties both public and private worth billions have been damaged, destroyed or both during this time. Nigerian's both indigenes from the North and non-indigenes, were fleeing for their lives, abandoning their properties, businesses and homes for safety. According to Adebayo, "families have been scattered, their ambitions cut short" (2014: 5), and many have become refugees in their own country, resulting in a humanitarian and security disaster. The situation is made untenable as the movement of human and material resources, especially to certain parts of the country, has been affected, as no individual wants to go and endanger their life. It has also exaggerated socio-cultural, ethnic and religious interactions amongst Nigerians and further pronounced the issues detracting from achieving national unity, as well as a sustainable developmental state.

Conclusion

Developmental state connotes state-oriented economic development, which is reflected in the infrastructural development, living conditions and standard of the people, as also important is the level of legitimacy accorded to the government based on its people-centred state development policies. This is why "it is referenced to as a state of growth whose ideological underpinnings are developmental and one that seriously attempts to deploy its administrative and political resources to the task of economic development" (Meyns and Musamba, 2010). Africa is in a perpetual flux; west to east, north to south, there is yet to be some kind of positive balance in all spheres of national affairs, particularly political leadership, economic potential, and cohesion in diversity. Especially, as over the past 2 decades in Africa, there seems to be more crises, conflict, and an expanding negative trend towards adopting policies and obligations that do not favour or give capability to the development initiatives of African states, and their security objectives. In Nigeria, the internal struggle for and of political, economic and socio-cultural leaning and interest, as also external interest and situations, has drastically affected the developmental objective and implementations in strategic areas to ensure national development, sustainability at all levels of government. Abundantly blessed with human and natural resources, and with the potential capability to harness and utilise all available resources, Nigeria has rather been overwhelmed, with no sense of direction, national planning, foresight and integrity that is compounded by the lack of leadership without ethnic, religious bias or favouritism. This factor has been the major stumbling block to the developmental state initiative of Nigeria, coming up to 60 years.

Recommendation

Nigeria must shed all the burdens of yesteryears and its numerous limitations and focus on the future. The conditions that favour the emergence of developmental states are not impossible, foreign, or alien, as shown and proved by African nations like Botswana, among others. These conditions are various, but the sensitive factors include: "Market mechanisms-which precludes establishment of investment-driven economy enhanced by private participation through liberalization and privatization; a relative state autonomy with powerful, competent/skilled, and embedded economic bureaucracy, a performance based state legitimacy, and; a state with development inclined elites, individuals, persons which implies presence of visionary, nationalistic and development-oriented leaders" (Nwokorie, 2014; 11), and the unprejudiced full participation of the citizens.

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